

Human Resource Management (HRM) Practices and the Level of Organizational Commitment of Employees in the Technical Vocational Institutions (TVIs) in Aklan

Bea Nyxie T. Señeris

National Teachers College, Quiapo, Manila, Philippines

Email: beanyxieseneris@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine the relationship between the extent of human resource management (HRM) practices and the level of organizational commitment of employees in the Technical Vocational Institutions (TVIs) in Aklan. It further discussed the extent of HRM practice as a whole and in terms of career opportunities, training and development, employment security, performance appraisal and compensation, rewards and benefits. Likewise, the level of organizational commitment as a whole and in terms of affective, normative and continuance commitment was discussed. Similarly, the significant differences in the level of organizational commitment when grouped as to their demographic profile were examined. This study utilized a descriptive-correlational method of research. There were 105 respondents that comprised 63 administrative and 42 teaching staff. The results show that TVIs in Aklan show a high extent of HRM practices. Further, TVI employees show normative commitment towards TVIs. Also, it has been found out that sex, educational background and civil status show significant differences in the level of organizational commitment, whereas, age, length of service and job classification of the respondents do not. Moreover, the results show that there is a moderate positive correlation between the extent of TVIs HRM practices and the respondents' level of organizational commitment.

Keywords: human resource management, organizational commitment, administrative staff, teaching staff, TVIs, Theory of Organizational Commitment

Received: 02 June 2024

Revised: 18 June 2024

Accepted: 25 June 2024

Copyright ♥ authors 2024

231

DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.12532257](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12532257)

1. INTRODUCTION

Paul J. Meyer, a businessman, quoted “Productivity is never an accident. It is always the result of a commitment to excellence, intelligent planning and focused effort.” (BrainyQuote.com). Employees are essential in running an organization for without them, achieving organizational goals will be near to impossible. They are considered as the true assets of the organization because they are the ones who contribute effectively towards the successful functioning of an organization. Hence, success in the organization is now dependent on the involvement of human resource management practices. To achieve the organizational goals and objectives, a company should possess skillful and innovative employees and make sure to retain them.

Retaining employees is a difficult task to do especially on the side of Human Resource Management. Combinations of different HR practices are implemented for the survival and sustainability of the organization (S. Lamba, N. Choudhary, 2013). Aneet (2006) said that good HR practices energize people in working in the organization. The commitment and motivation built through these can lead to hard work.

Aside from hard work, healthy HRM practices can help the company in maintaining good relationships with the employees. They will feel that they are valued and will interest them not to go against the company and therefore no chances of withdrawal of employees.

Employees’ commitment towards its organizations is one of the fundamental concepts in the HRM resulting in the increased performance. It should be in such a way that the individuals are willing to join the organization so that the organization can achieve a level of success (S. Nasiri, 2017). Further, it is one of the important factors in the organization that motivates employees to be attached with organizational goals. The commitment in the organization should not be in a way that employees are forced to stay in the organization because this would lead to failure to achieve the organizational goals and objectives.

Conceptually, the goal of this study was to examine the relationship between the extent of human resource management (HRM) practices and the level of organizational commitment of

employees in the Technical Vocational Institutions (TVIs) in Aklan based on the Theory of Organizational Commitment according to Meyer and Allen (1997), which are as follows: affective commitment (AC), normative commitment (NC) or cYontinuance commitment (CC).

According to the data from Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (TESDA) Aklan Provincial Office, there were twenty-two (22) private TVIs in Aklan. Only eighteen (18) of them were active while four (4) of them were applying for voluntary closure. Sixty-one percent (61%), exclusive of the TVIs applying for closure, were located in Kalibo, the capital of Aklan. Fourteen (14) out of the total active TVIs (78%) were family-owned corporations. They were offering different TESDA qualifications from different industry sectors such as in Tourism, Automotive and Land Transportation, Garments, Human Health/Health Care, ICT, Social, Community Development and other services.

With these, given with different variables, this study identified if the employees of these educational institutions were showing their commitment towards their organization through its HRM practices. This further helped the incorporators of each educational institution to work on its HRM practices, which were needed to improve, change or maintain. This could be their basis on how to treat their employees well in order for them to engage in a commitment within the school; a commitment that will last for a long time. Since 78% of them were family corporations, this study, in another way, could help the TVIs on how to treat most especially the non-family employees within their institution.

1.1 Theoretical Basis

1.1.1 Social Exchange Theory

This study was anchored on the concepts of Social Exchange Theory (SET) introduced by sociologist, George Homans (1958). It is used to understand when and why people, especially the organization's employees, choose to continue and end relationships. SET relies on getting the benefits to outweigh the costs. However, if the

costs outweigh the benefits, employees tend to end the relationship and find employers who will offer them more satisfaction in working.

Jose and Mampilly (2012) argued that the basic principle with SET was that employees view satisfying HRM practices as an organization's commitment towards them. Employees respond to this satisfaction to work is through positive behaviors like employee commitment. They exchanged their commitment for the benefits provided by the organization. SET was the point of focus and the underpinning theory used in this research. Based on this, the research proved as to what extent of HRM practices to be applied by TVIs to promise the employees' commitment to their own organizations.

There was a better understanding, most especially on the part of the administrators, as to what better HRM approach to use in exchange of the loyalty and trust of its employees and of course, their commitment to the organization they are working for.

1.1.2 Equity Theory of Motivation

This study was also anchored on the Equity Theory of Motivation concepts by John Stacey Adams (1963). It stated that employees are motivated by fairness. An employee's motivation level is correlated to his perception of equity, fairness and justice practiced by the management. The higher the employee's perception of equity, the more motivated they will work in the organization resulting in positive employee commitment. If someone thinks the opposite, they will be demotivated resulting in negative employee commitment to the organization.

While evaluating fairness, an employee compares his job input (e.g., time, effort, ability, commitment, etc.) to job output (e.g., compensation, benefits, recognition, security, etc.). An employee will also compare the same with that of another colleague of equal category or rank. As one of the underpinning theories of this

study, if employees perceive inequity, their commitment towards their organization will be affected.

1.1.3 Theory of Organizational Commitment

Another underpinning theory used in this study was the Theory of Organizational Commitment. According to Meyer and Allen (1997), organizational commitment is “a psychological state that characterizes the employees’ relationship with the organization and has implications for the decision to continue membership in the organization.”

The three-component model of commitment developed by Meyer and Allen (1997) proposed that employees’ commitment has three simultaneous components covering affective, normative and continuance organizational commitment.

Affective Commitment has emotion-based reasons. It is staying in the company because an employee wants to do so for the reason of emotional attachment. Continuance Commitment has cost-based reasons which means the employee is staying in the company just because he badly needs a job, and it will be such a waste to start over his employment career or maybe because of age requirements with other companies. Lastly, Normative Commitment is staying in the company because you must pay certain obligations.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Research Design

This study used a descriptive-correlational method of research. In this study, the researcher investigated the relationship between the extent of human resource management (HRM) practices and the level of organizational commitment of employees in the Technical Vocational Institutions (TVIs) in Aklan. The extent of HRM practices will include career opportunities, training and

Received: 02 June 2024

Revised: 18 June 2024

Accepted: 25 June 2024

Copyright ♥ authors 2024

235

DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.12532257](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12532257)

development, employment security, performance appraisal and compensation, rewards and benefits given to TVI employees. The level of organizational commitment towards the educational institution will include affective, normative and continuance commitment. This study also described the significant differences in the level of organizational commitment of the respondents when grouped as to their demographic profile such as sex, age, educational background, length of service, civil status and job classification.

2.2 Research Locale

The researcher conducted the study among Technical Vocational Institutions (TVIs) legally registered at Technical Education and Skills Development in Aklan (TESDA – Provincial Office of Aklan).

According to TESDA – Aklan, there are twenty-two (22) private TVIs duly registered. Only fourteen (14) of them are actively conducting their training programs while eight (8) of them are currently applying for temporary closure due to some reasons. So the study considered the fourteen (14) active TVIs.

2.3 Research Participants

The researcher utilized convenience sampling technique because during the visitation of the researcher, not all administrative and teaching staff were present. The respondents of the study had a total population of 105 TVI employees which included 63 administrative staff and 42 teaching staff from identified TVIs located in Aklan. In determining the sample size, the researcher used Slovin's formula with a margin error of 5%.

2.4 Data Gathering Instrument

The study utilized a two-part self-developed questionnaire, which was validated by four experts in the field of study: an Assistant Professor I of a State University, an Education Program Supervisor of the Department of Education, a Human Resource Manager and the Senior TESD

Specialist of TESDA-Aklan. The questionnaire was further validated using the criteria set by Good and Scates (1972). The following were part of the questionnaire:

Part 1 determined the employee's demographic profile which included sex, age, educational background, length of service, civil status and job classification.

Part 2.1 contained statements regarding the HRM practices of the TVIs. These included 50 statements about their career opportunities, training and development, employment security, performance appraisal and compensation, rewards and benefits. There were ten (10) statements for each HRM practice.

Part 2.2 was the TCM Employee Commitment Survey (Meyer and Allen, 1997). There were six (6) statements in all three (3) levels of commitment (AC, NC and CC) for a total of eighteen (18) statements.

To interpret the data in the relationship between the extent of HRM practices and the respondents' level of organizational commitment, the scale and verbal interpretation of Almeda, J. V., Capistrano, T. G., and Sarte, G. M. F. (2010) was used.

The comments and suggestions of the experts were considered for the revision of the instrument to ensure the instrument's validity.

2.5 Data Gathering Procedure

Firstly, the researcher secured an endorsement letter from TESDA-Aklan to be shown to the heads of each Technical Vocational Institutions (TVIs). Subsequently, a list of all administrative and teaching staff from each TVI was requested. Before the questionnaires were personally distributed, the researcher first explained to the respondents the nature and purpose of the study and that their responses were strictly confidential.

After retrieval of the instruments from the respondents, the responses were checked, tabulated, and statistically treated using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) for Windows Version 20.0 developed by the International Business Machines Corporation (IBM).

2.6 Data Analysis

The quantitative data gathered were tallied and treated using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software. The statistical tools used were frequency and percentage to describe the employee's demographic profile. Mean and standard deviation were used to determine the extent of HRM practices as a whole and in terms of (a) career opportunities, (b) training and development, (c) employment security, (d) performance appraisal and (e) compensation, rewards and benefits. Mean and standard deviation were also applied to determine the level of organizational commitment as whole and in terms of affective, normative and continuance commitment. T-test was used to determine if there is any significant difference in employees' level of organizational commitment when grouped according to sex, educational background, civil status and job classification. One-way ANOVA was used to determine if there is any significant difference in employees' level of organizational commitment when grouped according to age and length of service. Pearson's Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to determine the relationship between the extent of HRM practices and level of organizational commitment.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Demographic Profile of the Respondents

The demographic profile of the respondents is summarized in Table 1. This showed that the majority of the respondents were female, single, aged 22 to 30 years old, college graduate, with 1 to 3 years of service and were classified as administrative staff.

Table 1. Distribution of Respondents according to their Demographic Profile

Demographic Profile	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
WHOLE GROUP	105	100.00
SEX		
<i>Male</i>	40	38.10
<i>Female</i>	65	61.90
AGE		
<i>22 – 30 years old</i>	57	54.30
<i>31 – 39 years old</i>	30	28.60
<i>40 – above years old</i>	18	17.10
EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND		
<i>College graduate</i>	98	93.30
<i>Post-graduate</i>	7	6.70
LENGTH OF SERVICE		
<i>1 – 3 years</i>	46	43.80
<i>4 – 6 years</i>	26	24.80
<i>7 – 10 years</i>	19	18.10
<i>11 – above years</i>	14	13.30
CIVIL STATUS		
<i>Single</i>	61	58.10
<i>Married</i>	44	41.90
JOB CLASSIFICATION		
<i>Administrative Staff</i>	63	60.00
<i>Teaching Staff</i>	42	40.00

3.2 Extent of Human Resource Management Practices of TVIs

Table 2 presented the extent of HRM practices of the TVIs as a whole and in terms of career opportunities, training and development, employment security, performance appraisal and compensation, rewards and benefits. The extent of HRM practices of TVIs as a whole ($M = 3.97$, $SD = 0.59$) showed a High extent of practice. The extent of HRM practices of TVIs in terms of

career opportunities ($M = 4.02$, $SD = 0.62$), training and development ($M = 4.05$, $SD = 0.67$), employment security ($M = 3.84$, $SD = 0.74$), performance appraisal ($M = 3.83$, $SD = 0.78$) and compensation, rewards and benefits ($M = 4.10$, $SD = 0.75$) were all elaborated a High extent of practice. This showed that TVIs in the selected areas of human resource are practicing at a high degree a good management of employees. As Mehwish Jawaad et al. (2019) mentioned, it is critical in HR practices the training and enhancing the employees through attractive reward strategies and reinforcing the recruitment process.

The HRM practice Compensation, Rewards and Benefits showed the highest weighted mean at 4.10. This implied that on average, TVIs are giving their employees fair salary, proper benefits and an efficient compensation system. Just like in the study of Tessema, M. et al. (2013), employee recognition, pay and benefits were found to have an impact on job satisfaction of employees.

As to the two areas of HRM practices that scored the lowest, specifically employment security and performance appraisal, this could imply that even though it's still interpreted as High extent, there are few TVIs who are not performing highly in such critical areas in human resource. In terms of employment security, the study of Heydy Jimenez et al. (2017) revealed that job security is linked to job performance. The employees in their study had a tendency to correlate the feeling of security to their job performance. In the study of Farrell (2013), performance appraisal is a worthwhile tool to motivate employees.

Table 2. Extent of HRM Practices of TVIs

HRM Practice	Weighted Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (SD)	Extent of HRM Practice
Whole Group (N = 105)	3.97	0.59	High
<i>Career Opportunities</i>	4.02	0.62	High
<i>Training and Development</i>	4.05	0.67	High
<i>Employment Security</i>	3.84	0.74	High
<i>Performance Appraisal</i>	3.83	0.78	High
<i>Compensation, Rewards and Benefits</i>	4.10	0.75	High

3.3 Level of Organizational Commitment of TVI Employees

Table 3 presents the level of organizational commitment of TVI employees when taken as a whole and in terms of affective commitment, normative commitment and continuance commitment. The level of organizational commitment of the respondents as a whole ($M = 3.62$, $SD = 0.49$) exhibited a Moderate level of commitment. The level of organizational commitment of TVI employees in terms of affective commitment ($M = 3.60$, $SD = 0.70$) and continuance commitment ($M = 3.48$, $SD = 0.70$) both showed Moderate level of commitment. The normative commitment of the respondents ($M = 3.78$, $SD = 0.61$) revealed a High level of commitment. Employees of YTM Inc. at Calamba, Laguna, in the study of Jaron et al. (2015), reached a Moderate level of commitment as well in terms of affective and continuance commitment while on the other hand; some employees displayed a High level of normative commitment. This implied

Received: 02 June 2024

Revised: 18 June 2024

Accepted: 25 June 2024

Copyright ♥ authors 2024

241

DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.12532257](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12532257)

that some TVI employees were just staying in their company due to a feeling of obligation, which is a less personal commitment. It also meant that employees thought that it is just morally right to remain loyal to the company regardless of what their status or satisfaction it provides.

Continuance commitment has the lowest weighted mean among the three. This suggested that TVI employees were thinking that even if the costs of leaving their current company might be costly, they still have the experience and capability as an employee to find a new job again.

Table 3. Level of Organizational Commitment of TVI Employees

Organizational Commitment (OC)	Weighted Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (SD)	Levels of OC
Whole Group (N = 105)	3.62	0.49	Moderate
<i>Affective Commitment</i>	3.60	0.70	Moderate
<i>Normative Commitment</i>	3.78	0.61	High
<i>Continuance Commitment</i>	3.48	0.70	Moderate

3.4 Differences in the Level of Organizational Commitment of the Respondents

In this section, differences in the level of organizational commitment of the respondents according to their sex, age, educational background, length of service, civil status and job classification are presented.

Table 4.1 presents the independent samples T-test of the respondents in the level of organizational commitment when they are classified based on their *sex*, $t(103) = 3.79$, $p\text{-value} = 0.00$. Since the $p\text{-value} = 0.00$ is less than the alpha 0.05, so the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there is a significant difference between male and female in the level of organizational commitment. Female employees ($M = 3.75$, $SD = .46$) have higher organizational commitment than male employees ($M = 3.40$, $SD = .47$) among TVIs. This study supports the study of Mowday et al. (1979) that in terms of gender, males and females had significant differences and that females had a higher level of commitment towards work than males because they tried to do more for their

job status. This fact contradicts the study of Jena, R.K. (2015) stating that men has stronger organizational commitment than women. She implied that women think that the source of their commitment and identity is associated with their role in their own family. In other words, being a mother is more important than work. However, for men, work is their first choice. Moreover, women quit their jobs or stay away from office more often. The study of Emmanuel Affum-Osei et al. (2015) also found that there is a significant difference between the sex of the respondents and organizational commitment. It explained that men have higher organizational commitment due to their positions in the hierarchy. On the other hand, in the study Jaron, Sandoval and Garcia (2015), its assessment of organizational commitment in terms of sex has no significant difference.

Table 4.1. Difference in the Level of Organizational Commitment in terms of Sex

Demographic Profile	Weighted Mean	Level of Organizational Commitment
SEX		
Male	3.40	Moderate
Female	3.75	High
t(103) = 3.79	p-value = 0.00	p < 0.05 significant

Table 4.2 presents the one-way ANOVA test result of the respondents in the level of organizational commitment when they are classified based on their *age*, $F(2,102) = 1.21$, $p\text{-value} = 0.30$. Since the p-value is greater than the alpha 0.05, the null hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the ages of the respondents in the level of organizational commitment. All age groups are characterized by an acceptance of the TVIs values and shows willingness to exert efforts to remain in the organization. Though, those employees under age brackets 22 – 30 years old and 31 – 39 years old show moderate level of organizational commitment while employees 40 – above years old show high level of organizational commitment. Among the three age brackets, employees aged 22 – 30 years old has the lowest mean. It showed that since they are young, they still have more time and experience exploring other companies.

They think that they are still capable of applying and landing jobs to other companies. However, for employees aged 40 – above years old, it meant that since they are already old, might as well stay in the company, maybe because they have grown together with the company they are employed in. It meant that it is difficult to land on a new job at 40 years old and above. Correspondingly, the company has invested a lot in the training and development, compensation and benefits, they think that it is just right to return in the favour by showing commitment towards the organization.

The study of Mukti Clarence and Tony Sam George (2018) agrees in the result of this study that organizational commitment did not differ across age groups. In the study of Allen and Meyer (1993), they found and explained that the correlation between age and the three dimensions of organizational commitment was found to be significant. However, they said that it becomes difficult to investigate age as variables because there are other factors which affect the age of the respondents such as tenure, experience in life and career experience. Similarly, in another study, Vo Van Viet (2015) found a positive correlation between age and organizational commitment. It has been regarded as a positive predictor of organizational commitment because he believed that as the employees' age increased, their report on increased employment options.

Table 4.2. Difference in the Level of Organizational Commitment in terms of Age

Demographic Profile	Weighted Mean	Level of Organizational Commitment
AGE		
22 – 30 years old	3.56	Moderate
31 – 39 years old	3.65	Moderate
40 – above years old	3.76	High
F(2, 102) = 1.21	p-value = 0.30	p > 0.05 not significant

Table 4.3 presents the independent samples T-test of the respondents in the level of organizational commitment when they are classified based on their *educational background*,

Received: 02 June 2024

Revised: 18 June 2024

Accepted: 25 June 2024

Copyright ♥ authors 2024

244

$t(103) = 2.29$, $p\text{-value} = 0.02$. Since the p-value is less than the alpha 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there is a significant difference between the educational background of the respondents, whether they are college graduates ($M = 3.59$, $SD = .49$) or taking post-graduate studies ($M = 4.02$, $SD = .29$), in the level of organizational commitment. The study of Bakan et al. (2011) agrees with the result of this study that says the educational background of employees has significant differences in the level of their organizational commitment. As reported, the higher educated employees are, the more committed they are in the organization. The same with Salami (2008) and Jafri et al. (2013), they found out that educational background is a predictor of organizational commitment.

Between the two variables, employees who are post-graduate have the higher weighted mean at $M = 4.02$ compared to those who are college graduates which have a weighted mean of $M = 3.59$. In the study of Meyer and Allen (1997), they said that employees who were having higher levels of qualification experienced a higher level of organizational commitment (Meyer and Allen, 1997). This meant that because they possess more qualifications, they feel that the company values them more in terms of security, opportunities and give them advantages in the organization such as higher salary grade. For employees who were college graduates, they indicate a moderate level of organizational commitment. They display their acceptance willingness to the TVI but only partially. However, in the study of Chunghtai & Zafar (2006), they indicated that the more educational qualifications, the less organizational commitment. The reason was employees having more qualifications can find a job anywhere whereas having less qualification face difficulties in changing jobs and finding another suitable job.

Table 4.3. Difference in the Level of Organizational Commitment in terms of Educational Background

Demographic Profile	Weighted Mean	Level of Organizational Commitment
EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND		
<i>College Graduate</i>	3.59	Moderate
<i>Post-Graduate</i>	4.02	High
t(103) = 2.29	p-value = 0.02	p < 0.05 significant

Table 4.4 presents the one-way ANOVA test result of the respondents in the level of organizational commitment when grouped in terms of the respondents' *length of service*, $F(3, 101) = 0.31$, $p\text{-value} = 0.82$. Since the p-value is greater than the alpha 0.05, the null hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, there is no significant difference in the level of organizational commitment and respondents' length of service. This implied that regardless of how many years employee has been with the organization, it doesn't have any significant difference in the level of organizational commitment. They are still showing commitment in the TVI they are working for notwithstanding the number of years they have served the TVI. Chunghtai & Zafar (2006) proved in their study that tenure or the length of service of employees has no significant difference in the level of organizational commitment of employees. The same goes with the study of Jaron et al. (2015), length of service and level of organizational commitment of their employees did not show any significant difference as well. However, it does not confirm the study of Meyer and Allen (1997) which said that as an individual's length of service with a particular organization increases, an individual may develop commitment or attachment with the organization that makes it difficult to change jobs.

Employees who were the oldest in service, which is 11 years and above, have shown the highest commitment in the TVI they are working for having a weighted mean of $M = 3.71$ while for 10 years and below show only a moderate level of organizational commitment. This contradicts the study of Affum-Osei et al. (2015) which showed that employees who had 1-4 years job tenure

had the highest commitment compared to those who had 9 years and upper length of service. This showed that newly hired employees are showing their loyalty to the TVI and gaining some experience. They wanted to show their eagerness to work since they are newly employed.

Table 4.4. Difference in the Level of Organizational Commitment in terms of Length of Service

Demographic Profile	Weighted Mean	Level of Organizational Commitment
LENGTH OF SERVICE		
<i>1 – 3 years</i>	3.59	Moderate
<i>4 – 6 years</i>	3.65	Moderate
<i>7 – 10 years</i>	3.57	Moderate
<i>11 – above years</i>	3.71	High
F(3, 101) = 0.31	p-value = 0.82	p > 0.05 not significant

Table 4.5 presents the independent samples T-test of the respondents in the level of organizational commitment when they are classified based on their *civil status*, $t(103) = 2.29$, $p\text{-value} = 0.02$. Since the p-value is less than the alpha 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there is a significant difference between the single ($M = 3.53$, $SD = .49$) and married employees ($M = 3.74$, $SD = .47$) in the level of organizational commitment. Civil status proved to be a consistent predictor of organizational commitment (Jena, R.K., 2015). Based on the study of Jaron et al. 2015, they also found a significant difference between civil status and organizational commitment of their employees. The results of this current study implied that married TVI employees, having higher commitment ($M = 3.74$) than single TVI employees ($M = 3.53$), have more family responsibilities and because of that they need more stability and security in their jobs, therefore, they are likely to be more committed to their current organization than those who are unmarried. It will take so much time and wasted money if they are looking for new jobs instead of earning and gaining commitment to their current organization. Single TVI employees in this study are showing moderate levels of organizational commitment. This showed that they still are

committed and wanted to work with the TVI they are currently employed with but maybe sooner or later, they will go out and look for more work experience. Since they are still single, they don't have any family responsibilities like married employees have. On the other hand, in the study of Clarence, Mukti & George, Tony (2018), it indicated that there was no significant relationship in terms of civil status and organizational commitment and across all three levels of organizational commitment.

Table 4.5. Difference in the Level of Organizational Commitment in terms of Civil Status

Demographic Profile	Weighted Mean	Level of Organizational Commitment
CIVIL STATUS		
<i>Single</i>	3.53	Moderate
<i>Married</i>	3.74	High
t(103) = 2.29	p-value = 0.02	p < 0.05 significant

Table 4.6 presents the independent samples T-test of the respondents in the level of organizational commitment when they are classified according to their **job classification**, $t(103) = 0.21$, $p\text{-value} = 0.83$. Since the p-value is greater than the alpha 0.05, the null hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the administrative and teaching staff in the level of organizational commitment. The results of the study oppose the study of Tolentino, R. (2013) that said between the academic and administrative personnel of one of the chartered universities in Manila, she found out that academic and administrative personnel differ significantly in terms of organizational commitment. She further explained that academic personnel showed higher commitment than administrative personnel. This can be explained by the fact that university teachers during interviews said that they enjoy teaching in the universities because of the qualifications of the students. And they derived more fulfillment in teaching while some derived their commitment because of higher salary. Conversely, in the study of Poliquit et al. (2018), they found out that employees, specifically the teaching and administrative staff of

higher education in the Philippines do not manifest high or ideal commitment either towards their assigned job or towards the organization in general.

Administrative and teaching staff of TVIs both showed moderate level of organizational commitment towards the TVI they are currently working in. This showed that both the administrative and teaching staff showed their willingness to work in the organization. They feel their goals align with the TVI and thus show their commitment by staying. They both show moderate levels of organizational commitment maybe because of some complications that are currently occurring among TVIs now. Because there is always a change of leadership at provincial level, there are inconsistencies that result in unexpected conflicts within TESDA and TVIs. Therefore, there were employees who are not so sure if they will still be fully committed to the TVI they are working in because of such conflicts.

Table 4.6. Difference in the Level of Organizational Commitment in terms of Job Classification

Demographic Profile	Weighted Mean	Level of Organizational Commitment
JOB CLASSIFICATION		
<i>Administrative</i>	3.62	Moderate
<i>Teaching</i>	3.60	Moderate
t(103) = 0.21	p-value = 0.83	p > 0.05 not significant

3.5 Relationship Between the Extent of HRM Practices and Level of Organizational Commitment of TVIs

Table 5 presents the relationship of the extent of HRM practices and the level of organizational commitment of the respondents ($r = 0.41$, $p\text{-value} = 0.00$). Since the p-value is less than alpha 0.05, there is a moderate positive correlation between the HRM practices and the level of organizational commitment of the TVI employees. Therefore, the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the two variables is rejected. This showed that as the TVI's extent of HRM practices goes up, the level of organizational commitment of its employees goes

up as well. Likewise, if the extent of HRM practices goes down, the employees' level of organizational commitment goes down as well. The result agrees with the findings of Bal et al. (2014) which revealed that there is a medium positive relationship between organizational commitment and HR practices ($r = 0.47$, $p\text{-value} = 0.01$). They explained that effective HRM practices of the company can help increase its employees' organizational commitment levels. Roles such as recruitment and selection, participation of the employees in the decision making, training and development, performance evaluation, working conditions and compensation management can help improve organizational commitment. The results of this study also confirm the study made by Mehwish Jawaad et al. (2019) that found positive associations among the employees' perception of the employment of proper HR practices and stronger organizational commitment along with high level of job satisfaction.

Theoretically, this study confirms Social Exchange Theory (George Homans, 1958) that when organizations deliver their intent in social exchange relationships by investing in effective systems of HRM, employees respond by becoming more empathetic toward the organizational goals and reciprocate with behaviors that benefit the company. Just what Jose and Mampilly (2012) claimed that employees view satisfying HRM practices as an organization's commitment towards them. In return, they respond to this satisfaction to work through positive behaviors like commitment.

This study also associates in the Equity Theory of Motivation (John Adams, 1963) that stated employees' motivation level is correlated to their perception of equity, fairness and justice practiced by the management. It means that the higher the employee's perception of equity, the more motivated they will be working in the company which results in positive employee commitment. If they think otherwise, they will be demotivated resulting in negative employee commitment to the organization.

This means that TVIs, specifically to the heads and administrators, in exchange of the loyalty and trust of the employees, should be provided with effective HRM practices such as in their career development, training and enhancement, security of tenure and compensation management. In this way, TVIs can also help attain their own company's organizational goals

easily because they maintain and improve their employees' capacity and skills. Since employees are committed, they do not intend on leaving the company, thus the company has lessened its training and investment to new employees.

Table 5. Relationship between the extent of HRM Practices and the level of Organizational Commitment of the respondents

PEARSON'S CORRELATION			
	<i>r</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Significance</i>
<i>Extent of HRM Practices of TVI Employees</i>			
<i>Level of Organizational Commitment</i>	0.41	0.00	Significant
MODERATE POSITIVE RELATIONSHIP			

4. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

4.1 Conclusions

The following conclusions were drawn based on the results of the study:

1. Majority of the respondents were female, single, aged 22 to 30 years old, college graduate, with 1 to 3 years of service and were classified as administrative staff.
2. The HRM practices of TVIs as a whole and in terms of career opportunities, training and development, employment security, performance appraisal and compensation, rewards and benefits all indicated a High extent of practice. This shows that TVIs are practicing at a high degree a good management of employees especially in terms of giving compensation, rewards and benefits to its employees.
3. TVI employees showed a moderate level of affective commitment and continuance commitment which means that they stay in the company because they want to and because

they are partially emotionally-attached to it. It also means that if they leave the company now, it would be too costly for them to look for new jobs and also because they exerted efforts to remain due to the benefits they receive. Differently, TVI employees showed a high level of normative commitment which means they stay in the company because they are obliged to, which is a less personal commitment. They think that it is just morally right to stay in the organization and remain loyal regardless of how much satisfaction and status it provides.

4. The level of organizational commitment among TVI employees is not determined by age, length of service and job classification, but by other factors such as sex, educational background and civil status.
5. There is a moderate positive relationship between the extent of HRM practices and the TVI employees' level of organizational commitment which means that as the extent of HRM practice goes up, the level of organizational commitment goes up too. Therefore, to remain the TVI employees organizationally committed, TVIs should exert effort on taking care of their employees by providing them career opportunities, provide them with training to develop them professionally and give them fair and proper compensation, rewards and benefits.

4.2 Recommendations

Based on the conclusions, the researcher presents the following recommendations:

1. The TVI Administrators should continue their high extent of HRM practice in order for their employees to remain committed and loyal to them. Such HRM practices will motivate them to work and help attain the organizational mission and goals. By keeping the valued employees, the TVI will reduce and minimize their expenditures by training newly hired employees. The TVI administrators should revisit together with their HR Manager/Personnel Manager their HR policies to develop plans on how to increase their employees affective and continuance commitment like being more compassionate and sympathetic to them and also, by providing them with training to develop and enhance

career-wise, compensation, rewards and benefits that is fair in terms of work done and experience.

2. For the TVI employees, they should be given equal opportunities in terms of fair compensation and training needs for them to stay in the organization. Through these, the TVI can help their employees to achieve their personal goals and help develop them professionally. Likewise, help the TVI achieve its mission and goals in exchange for proper employee management.
3. The Human Resource/Personnel Manager/Officers should continue to develop their employees' career professionally by assessing and providing them with training and enhancements. They should also revisit their HR policies, procedures and standards of their organization so as to provide equal opportunities for both administrative and teaching staff and other employees. In this way, the organization can provide and promote healthy workplace relationships among employees and TVI administrators.
4. The researcher should disseminate the results of this study for the TVIs to know that they should be providing their employees with proper care and give equal opportunities to them in terms of training and compensation. This will help the TVI administrators to be educated more about HRM practices and organizational commitment. For those TVIs who do not have their HR manual, this could be their basis in making and starting their own. Through this study, TVIs should propose to the management that they should have rewards and service recognition to those employees who have served their organization well. These will keep the TVI employees motivated and be committed to the TVI they are working in.
5. For further research, one could study what kind of organizational commitment (i.e. affective, normative and continuance) does each demographic group have. The future researchers could also study the impact of organizational commitment to turnover intention or job performance. Respondents could be interviewed to gain deeper understanding of their organizational commitment.

REFERENCES

- 1) Adams, J. S. (1963). Toward an Understanding of Inequity. *Journal of Abnormal and Social Psychology*, 67, 422-436.
- 2) Emmanuel Affum-Osei, Ebenezer Acquah, Phinihas Acheampong. (2015) Relationship between Organizational Commitment and Demographic Variables: Evidence from a Commercial Bank in Ghana. *American Journal of Industrial and Business Management*, 2015, 5, 769-778.
- 3) Almeda, J. V., Capistrano, T. G., & Sarte, G. M. F. (2010). *Elementary statistics*. Diliman, Quezon City: University of the Philippines Press.
- 4) Aneet (2006). A Study of HRM Practices and their Impact in Selected Units of Textile Industry of Northern Region. *Punjab University, Chandigarh*.
- 5) Bakan, İ., Büyükbeşe, T., Erşahan, B. “An Investigation of Organizational Commitment and Education Level among Employees”, *International Journal of Emerging Sciences* 1(3): 231-245, 2011.
- 6) Bal, Y., Bozkurt, S. & Ertemsir, E. (2014). Determining the influence of HRM practices on increasing organizational commitment: an empirical research from Turkey. Portorož, Slovenia International Conference 2014. <http://www.toknowpress.net/ISBN/978-961-6914-09-3/papers/ML14-674.pdf>
- 7) Clarence, Mukti & George, Tony. (2018). Role of Demographic Variables in Organizational Commitment among Catholic College Teachers. 2347-4793.
- 8) Farrell (2013). An investigation into Performance Appraisal effectiveness from the perception of Employees in an Irish Consumer Services Company. *National College of Ireland*.
- 9) Heydy Jimenez et al. (2017). Perceived Job Security and its Effects on Job Performance: Unionized VS. Non-unionized Organizations. *The International Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities Invention*, vol.4, Issue 8, August 2017.
- 10) Homans, G. C. (1958). Social Behavior as Exchange. *American Journal of Sociology* 63, no. 6, pp. 597-606. <https://doi.org/10.1086/222355>

- 11) Jafri, M.H., Lhamo, T. (2013), Organizational commitment and work of performance in regular and contract faculties of Royal University of Bhutan. *Journal of Contemporary Research in Management*, 8(2), 47-58.
- 12) Jaron, Sandoval and Garcia (2015). An assessment of organizational commitment among selected administrative employees of Yazaki-Torres Manufacturing, Inc. *CAS Research Journal. Psychological Research* Vol. 2. No. 2. <http://lpulaguna.edu.ph/wp-content/uploads/2016/10/AN-ASSESSMENT-OF-ORGANIZATIONAL-COMMITMENT-AMONG-SELECTED-ADMINISTRATIVE-EMPLOYEES-OF-YAZAKI-TORRES-MANUFACTURING.pdf>
- 13) Jawaad, Mehwish & Amir, Abeera & Bashir, Aideed & Hasan, Tania. (2019). Human Resource Practices and Organizational Commitment: The Mediating Role of Job Satisfaction in Emerging Economy. *Cogent Business & Management*. 6. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/332551918_Human_Resource_Practices_and_Organizational_Commitment_The_Mediating_Role_of_Job_Satisfaction_in_Emerging_Economy
- 14) Jena, R.K. (2015). An assessment of demographic factors affecting organizational commitment among shift workers in India. *Institute of Management Technology*, Vol. 20, pp. 59-77)
- 15) Jose, Geetha & Mampilly, Sebastian Rupert (2012). Satisfaction with HR Practices and Employee Engagement: A Social Exchange Perspective. *Journal of Economics and Behavioural Studies*, # 7, Vol. 4, July 2012. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/235790288_'Satisfaction_with_HR_Practices_and_Employee_Engagement_A_Social_Exchange_Perspective'_Journal_of_Economics_and_Behavioural_Studies_7_Vol_4_July_2012/citation/download.
- 16) Lamba, S. & Choudhary N., (2013). Impact of HRM Practices on Organizational Commitment of Employees. *International Journal of Advancements in Research & Technology, Volume 2, Issue 4*. <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/f37a/720746c51e0ce2e7f0055cd928e2b628ce64.pdf>
- 17) Meyer J and Allen N (1997). *Commitment in the Workplace: Theory, Research, and Application*. Sage Publications.

- 18) Meyer J and Allen N (1997). TCM Employee Commitment Survey. Department of Psychology. University of Western Ontario. <https://www.employeecommittment.com/TCM-Employee-Commitment-Survey-Academic-Package-2004.pdf>
- 19) Mowday, R. & Steers, R. (1979). The measurement of organizational commitment. *Journal of Vocational Behavior* 14, 224-247. https://www.academia.edu/3379532/The_measurement_of_organizational_commitment_1
- 20) Nasiri, S. (2016). Human Resource Management, Organizational Commitment and Organizational Performance: Development, Test and Correction of the Causal Model. *International Review of Management and Marketing*, 2017, 7(3), 86-92. Department of Electrical and Computer, Sirjan University of technology, Sirjan, Kerman Province, Iran. <https://dergipark.org.tr/en/download/article-file/367705>. Nigerian paramilitary organization. *International Journal of Business & Economic*.
- 21) Paul J. Meyer Quotes. (n.d.). BrainyQuote.com. Retrieved September 20, 2019, from BrainyQuote.com Web site: https://www.brainyquote.com/quotes/paul_j_meyer_393225
- 22) Poliquit, W. & Ferrater-Gimena, J. & Etcuban, J. (2018) Grasping the Organizational Commitment of Employees in a Higher Education Institution in the Philippines. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*
- 23) Salami, S.O. (2008) Demographic and Psychological Factors Predicting Organizational Commitment among Industrial Workers. *Anthropologist*, 10, 31-38. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09720073.2008.11891026>
- 24) Tolentino, R. (2013). Organizational Commitment and Job Performance of the Academic and Administrative Personnel. *International Journal of Information Technology and Business Management*. Vol.15 No.1. <https://www.jitbm.com/JITBM%2015th%20volume/5%20Organization%20Commitment.pdf>